

4a (62%), m.p. 256° (Found : C, 51.00 ; H, 3.50 ; N, 19.00. C₁₃H₁₀N₄S₂O requires : C, 49.65 ; H, 3.44 ; N, 19.31%) ; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 600 (C=N), 1 730 (C=O), 3 100 (CH₂) and 3 250 cm⁻¹ (OH) ; δ (TFA) 2.15–2.25 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.5 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.1–7.6 (5H, m, Ar-H) ; 4g, ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 640 (C=N), 1 690 (C=O), 3 100 (CH₂) and 3 300 cm⁻¹ (OH).

5-Arylidine-[3-(4-substituted-phenyl)]-2-[3-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl]imino]-thiazolid-4-ones (5a–o) : The compounds were prepared by Knoevenagel condensation of thiazolidinone with aromatic aldehyde using acetate ion as a base. To a solution of benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) and the thiazolidinone (4 ; 0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) was added anhydrous sodium acetate (0.015 mol) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4–5 h with occasional shaking. It was cooled and poured into crushed ice. The solid separated out was filtered, washed successively with water and recrystallised from alcohol (Table 1) : 5l (65%), m.p. 250° (Found : C, 62.60 ; H, 4.40 ; N, 13.10. C₂₂H₂₀N₄OS₂ requires : C, 62.85 ; H, 4.76 ; N, 13.33%) ; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 600 (C=N), 1 700 (C=O) and 2 950 cm⁻¹ (CH) ; 5a, ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 610 (C=N), 1 710 (C=O) and 2 900 cm⁻¹ (CH) ; δ (TFA) 2.20–2.30 (3H, s, CH₃) and 7.2–7.8 (10H, m, ArH).

Antibacterial activity : Compounds 4 and 5 were evaluated for their *in vitro* growth inhibitory activity against the bacteria *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, using the agar-plate diffusion technique¹¹.

From the antibacterial data it was observed that the compounds 4c, 4g, 4h, 4k–m, 5b, 5c, 5g, 5h, 5l and 5n were more toxic to bacteria. A study of the structure-activity relationship showed that there was an increase in the antibacterial property of the compounds with an increase in the alkyl side chain from methyl to propyl. The chlorotoxophore also contributed to increase the activity.

Antifungal activity : Antifungal activity of a few representative compounds was performed against *Aspergillus niger*, *Chetomium globosum* and *Penicillin brevicompactum* using agar-growth technique¹². The compounds in general showed marginal inhibition except compounds 4c, 4d, 4m and 5d which exhibited good inhibition of the growth of fungal colony against all strains used. Introduction of arylidene group at 5-position in thiazolidinone nucleus showed marked fall in the activity.

Antiviral activity : Compounds 4 and 5 were also screened¹³ as antiviral agents against Sunnhemp rosette virus (SRV—a strain of TMV) maintained on host *Cymopsis tetragonoloba* plants. The results revealed that the best compounds of the series were 4c, 4f, 4h, 4k, 4m, 5c, 5f, 5g and 5m (50% inhibition). The variation of alkyl side chain had no note-worthy effect on the activity but the presence of chloro group resulted in a marked increase in the activity.

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Fatty Acids and Sterols from *Melastoma melabathricum*

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MELASTOMA melabathricum Linn.^{1,2} (*Melastomataceae*) an endemic plant of Tripura, Assam and Bangladesh, possesses various medicinal uses³. Previous communications reported the presence of a purple dyestuff, β -sitosterol, melastomic acid, amino acids and aliphatic compounds in different parts of the plant^{3,4}. We now report the isolation and identification of fatty acids and a few more sterols from the aerial parts of the plant.

The aerial parts of *M. melabathricum* were collected from the tilla areas of Agartala in May 1984. Air-dried milled aerial parts (2.0 kg) of the plant was Soxhleted with petrol (b.p. 60–80°), and the crude petrol extract (15.0 g) was chromatographed

through silica gel. The petrol eluate on evaporation of solvent gave a oily residue (3.5 g) : protein content ($N \times 6.25$), 2.8%; iodine value (Wij's/30 min), 35.8; and saponification equivalent, 157.0. The oily residue (2.0 g) was saponified with 1 *N* methanolic KOH (50 ml) for 2 h in an atmosphere of N_2 . The solvent methanol was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue diluted with water. The unsaponifiable matter was recovered by extraction of the aqueous layer with diethyl ether. The ether layer was dried and evaporated to get a residue of unsaponifiable matter (0.6 g). The mixed fatty acids were obtained by acidification of the aqueous layer with dilute HCl to pH 2–3 followed by extraction with diethyl ether. The ether layer was dried and evaporated to get an oil of fatty acids (1.1 g).

Me-esters of fatty acids were reported with diazomethane in the usual manner and these esters mixtures were purified through silica gel column and analysed by glc technique on a Pye Unicam 104 gas chromatograph equipped with a FID and a 10% PEGA column; operating conditions: injection port temperature 200°, column temperature 190°, FID temperature 210°, carrier gas N_2 at flow rate 50 ml min^{-1} , chart speed 320 mm h^{-1} . The Me-esters were identified⁵ by co-glc with authentic samples. Their equivalent chain length values and relative retention times (with respect to 18 : 0) as well as their relative abundances (in terms of peak areas) are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EQUIVALENT CHAIN LENGTHS (ECL), RELATIVE RETENTION TIMES (RR_i) AND RELATIVE ABUNDANCE OF Me-ESTERS

Me-esters of fatty acids	ECL	RR _i	Relative abundance %
Lauric (12 : 0)	12.00	0.13	2.59
Lauroleic (12 : 1, n-3)	12.18	0.15	5.93
Myristic (14 : 0)	14.00	0.26	7.91
Myristoleic (14 : 1, n-5)	14.49	0.30	7.43
— (14 : 2)	15.38	0.41	8.63
Palmitic (16 : 0)	16.00	0.52	35.79
— (16 : 2, n-6)	17.31	0.80	2.03
Stearic (18 : 0)	18.00	1.00	4.76
Oleic (18 : 1, n-9)	18.92	1.11	4.16
Linoleic (18 : 2, n-6)	18.90	1.35	2.44
Behenic (22 : 0)	22.00	3.06	1.05
Unidentified —	—	—	17.88

The presence of unsaturated Me-esters was also confirmed by catalytic hydrogenation of a part of the ester mixture with 10% Pd–C followed by glc analysis under identical condition when the peaks of 12 : 1, 14 : 1, 14 : 2, 16 : 2, 18 : 1 and 18 : 2 fatty acids were not found in the chromatogram.

Unsaponifiable matter (0.5 g) was chromatographed through silica gel. Petrol–benzene (1 : 3) eluate on evaporation of solvent gave a residue which on repeated crystallisation from MeOH–CHCl₃ mixture gave colourless crystalline solid (0.1 g) m.p. 132°; homogenous on tlc; showed

positive Salkowski test and Liebermann–Burchard test for steroids. It showed ν_{max} (KBr) 3 440 (OH) and 1 640 cm^{-1} (unsaturation). Its ¹H nmr spectra (100 MHz, CDCl₃) displayed methyl signals at δ 0.67 (s), 0.80 (d, *J* 6.5 Hz), 0.84 (d, *J* 6.5 Hz), 0.86 (t), 0.92 (s) and 1.00 (s), one proton methine signal at δ 3.50 (m) and one olefinic proton signal at δ 5.34 (s, br) which were suggestive for C₂₉– Δ^5 sterol structure⁶. The El-mass spectrum was more diagnostic to ascertain the skeletal structure. It showed some significant peaks at *m/z* 414, 412, 400, 399, 397, 396, 385, 381, 315, 314, 303, 300, 281, 275, 273, 271, 255, 253, 231, 215, 213, 95, 93, 91, 69 and 55 which can be best rationalised by considering the solid to be a mixture of phytosterols^{6,7}, sitosterol, stigmasterol, campesterol and cholesterol. In order to confirm this fact by glc technique, the solid (0.05 g) was acetylated with acetic anhydride and pyridine and the usual work up of the acetylated mixture gave a crystalline product (0.02 g), m.p. 82–3°. The acetylated product was subjected to glc on the gas chromatograph using 3% OV-17 and SE-30 columns maintaining column temperature 260°, injection port and FID temperature 280° and carrier gas N_2 at flow rate 50 ml min^{-1} . It was identified^{8,9} as acetates of cholesterol [cholest-5-en-3 β -ol; RR_i in OV-17 and SE-30 columns, respectively, 1.00; 1.00; relative abundance, 26.4%], campesterol [(24*R*)-24-methylcholest-5-en-3 β -ol; 1.31; 1.30; 15.8%]; stigmasterol [24*S*]-24-ethylcholesta-5*F*-22-dien-3 β -ol; 1.43; 1.42; 12.5%] and β -sitosterol [(24*R*)-24-ethylcholest-5-en-3 β -ol; 1.63; 1.61; 45.3%]. Only β -sitosterol has been reported before from the roots of this plant.

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